

777372 - RESOLUTE

Research Empowerment on Solute Carriers

**WP1 – Generation of
reagents and cell lines to
allow system-wide study of
the SLC family**

D1.3 SLC KO in HEK293

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Abstract

RESOLUTE aims to unlock the therapeutic potential of solute carriers (SLCs) in a systematic and coordinated effort. To reach this goal, loss- and gain-of-function studies using SLC knock-out (KO) and overexpression (OE) cell models are crucial. For deliverable D1.2, we generated KO clones in a panel of human cancer cell lines for about 300 SLCs (see D1.2 report). To provide a second KO model in a different cell type, it was originally planned to also generate KO clones for >80% of SLCs in the Jump-In T-REx HEK 293 cell line. However, as agreed among the consortium partners, a second KO model for all targets in a cell line that is not more physiologically relevant than the human cancer cell lines may offer little additional scientific value. We therefore focused on generating HEK KO clones only for priority targets for which this second KO model was requested by a consortium member. To genetically delete these targets, we transduced Jump-In T-REx HEK 293 cells with the same CRISPR/Cas9 vectors that have already been used to generate SLC KO clone in human cancer cell lines (D1.2 report). In a first attempt to generate Jump-In T-REx HEK 293 KO models, we identified KO clones for 30 targets. Due to the general assembly decision to cease these efforts for all targets, further attempts were put on hold until recently when a selection of five priority SLCs was identified as targets where a HEK KO model would be potentially valuable. Generating these KO (and subsequently rescue/KO-OE) models will mainly support the development of functional assays for targets where the HEK293 cell line is not replaceable as model and endogenous expression hinders the assay readout.

Methods

Lentiviral CRISPR/Cas9 KO vectors:

To introduce frame-shifting mutations into SLC genes in cancer cell lines, we cloned several sets of CRISPR/Cas9 gRNAs into the pLentiCRISPRv2 vector as reported in D1.2.

KO pool generation and single cell cloning:

293T packaging cells were transfected with pLentiCRISPR vectors and lentiviral packaging constructs to produce infectious viral particles. The majority of gRNAs were tested in Jump-In T-REx HEK 293 cells to assess their editing efficiency before they were used to generate KO clones in either of the cell models. For this, a part of the viral supernatant was transduced into Jump-In T-REx HEK 293 cells and cells from the KO pool were collected after antibiotic selection. Genomic DNA was harvested and editing efficiency was determined by NGS as described below. Generally, a vector had to lead to at least 60% edited alleles in the HEK pools to be considered as experimentally validated. These KO pools were then used for single cell cloning, either by limited dilution seeding or FACS. Single cells were sorted into 96-well dishes and expanded for 2-3 weeks before freezing and harvesting genomic DNA for genotyping. Usually, we aimed to generate 12 single-cell clones per KO pool to have a high chance of identifying at least two KO clones per target.

To generate WT controls that underwent the same procedures as the KO clones, we transduced Jump-In T-REx HEK 293 cells with gRNAs targeting the Renilla luciferase gene which is absent in the human genome. Selection and single cell sorting of these cell lines was performed as for KO clones to match them as close as possible.

Genotyping procedure:

The vast majority of generated clones were genotyped using an NGS-based approach. For this, a 200-600 bp fragment containing the gRNA cut site was amplified with primer that contain partial Illumina adapter sequences as 5'overhangs. Using a universal set of Illumina barcoding primer (12 x i7 barcodes and 8 x i5 barcodes), we then introduced unique barcode combinations as well as the remaining part of the Illumina adapters to the PCR products. Samples were then purified and multiplexed to assemble the Illumina library. In theory, 96 clones could be genotyped with the available barcode combinations. Since also the sequence of the PCR amplicon itself can be used to demultiplex the NGS reads, up to several thousand clones could be multiplexed in one sequencing run. However, for practical reasons we usually multiplexed and sequenced only 350-450 samples together in one run. For the analysis of the NGS genotyping data, we developed a custom software (CREScout) that allows the automatic detection of frame-shifting and deletions and insertions in our genes of interest. As an alternative genotyping approach (which was also used to confirm the genotype of about 50 KO clones after

expansion), we sequenced the amplified PCR products by Sanger sequencing and determined mutations using the ICE tool (Synthego).

After KO clones were identified, the original freeze stocks were thawed, expanded, and used for quality control and a set of new freeze stocks. If more than two KO clones were identified for one target, we chose up to four clones for expansion. However, only two of the clones were further analysed while the rest was frozen as backup clones.

Quality control and cell line characterization:

a. Mycoplasma testing:

To monitor potential mycoplasma contaminations in our lab, we regularly tested cell lines by PCR according to the guidelines of the service provider (Eurofins). Furthermore, media was visually monitored for bacterial contaminations after culturing without antibiotics. We confirmed the absence of mycoplasma contamination for a total of 14 Jump-In T-REx HEK 293 KO clones, indicating a clean lab environment.

b. RNA-seq:

For transcriptomics analysis, 5×10^5 cells of each KO clone were seeded in two wells of a 12-well dish 24 hours prior to sample preparation. RNA was purified in replicates using a Qiagen 96 RNA purification kit (with on column DNase digestion) at CeMM and sent for library generation and deep sequencing on a NovaSeq machine at Boehringer Ingelheim. To this date, we sequenced two Jump-In T-REx HEK 293 KO clones in replicates for 18 targets. To characterize the transcriptional profile of these KO clones, RNA-seq data of two KO clones and two WT controls cells transduced with a Renilla gRNA were used to quantify endogenous transcripts. Differential expression of genes was determined using DESeq2.

Results

Due to the changed aim of this deliverable, KO clones were only generated for 30 targets so far. However, we generated and stored Jump-In T-REx HEK 293 KO pools with validated gRNAs for 282 targets which allows us to rapidly create KO clones on demand. We are currently in the process of sorting eight of these KO pools to provide KO clones for all requested targets in early 2022. We may attempt to generate Jump-In T-REx HEK 293 KO clones for a small number or priority targets upon request until the end of 2022 as long as time and resources allow it.

Discussion

During the general assembly of the 2nd RESOLUTE consortium meeting in Krems in 2019, it was decided that the resources required to generate a second KO model for all targets would be better invested into the characterization of the Jump-In T-REx HEK 293 WT-OE cell lines (see D1.5 report). These efforts aimed to determine the subcellular localization of all SLCs using high-content imaging with co-staining for the main organelles and cellular compartments, which will help to identify the optimal SLC version to generate the KO-OE cancer cell lines. All consortium partners agreed that the data coming from this localization effort would be more valuable than an additional KO model in a cell line that is not more physiologically relevant than the human cancer cell lines we used to generate the first KO model. Moreover, we anticipated that these additional KO cell lines could not be thoroughly analysed within the available time and resources.

Conclusion

The aim to generate Jump-In T-REx HEK 293 KO models for >80% of SLCs has been changed to an on-demand KO generation service for special targets. Since Jump-In T-REx HEK 293 KO pools have already been generated for 282 targets, we will be able to timely fulfil requests for KO clones over the remaining course of the consortium.

Distribution of cell lines and repository of primary data

All Jump-In T-REx HEK 293 KO clones will eventually be available for research purpose to non-RESOLUTE institutions. After a reagent release proposal for these cell lines has been approved by the consortium (planned for 2022), CeMM will be able to ship these KO clones to interested parties that have signed an MTA that regulates the usage of the cells. A deposition of the Jump-In T-REx HEK 293 KO cell lines at a cell bank is not possible since the General Terms and Conditions of Sale for the parental cell line does not allow a distribution of the original or modified cell lines against any kind of fee which would be also required for non-profit repositories to cover their running costs.

RNA-seq data will be made available to the public via the RESOLUTE web portal after the corresponding data release has been approved by the consortium partners (planned for spring 2022). RNA-seq data will in addition be deposited at the European Nucleotide Archive (ENA).

The RESOLUTE web portal will provide an overview on the Jump-In T-REx HEK 293 KO cell lines and will also allow to download sequencing results (raw data) for all experiments. Transcript and gene quantification (processed data) as well as the results of the differential expression analyses (analysed data) will be not only available for download in tabular format but can also be interactively explored via a dashboard visualization.